

Evaluation of the Effect of Daytime Power Napping on Depression, Stress and Sleep According to Working Method: Prospective Cohort Study

Zortuk Okkes, MD¹, Dersuneli Yesim², Tolan Ozlem, PhD³

Keywords: Naps, shift workers, depression, stress, sleep quality

¹ Emergency Medicine Department, Defne Government Hospital, Hatay, Türkiye

² Clinical Psychology, Muş Alparslan University, Muş, Türkiye

³ Clinical Psychology, Dicle University, Diyarbakır, Türkiye

1. Dr. Okkes Zortuk, o.zortuk@gmail.com , 05416104204, ORCID: 0000-0001-6776-2702, Emergency Medicine Department, Defne Government Hospital, Hatay, Türkiye
2. Res. Assist. Yesim Dersuneli, yesimdersuneli@gmail.com , +90 534 817 59 80, ORCID: 0000-0002-8335-1409, Clinical Psychology, Muş Alparslan University, Muş, Türkiye
3. Assist. Prof. Dr. Ozlem Tolan, ozlemtolan@gmail.com , 05325488722, ORCID: 0000-0002-8128-6498 , Clinical Psychology, Dicle University, Diyarbakır, Türkiye

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ökkeş ZORTUK

Affiliation: Emergency Medicine Department, Defne Government Hospital

Phone: +905416104204

Fax: 0326 227 15 15

Mail: o.zortuk@gmail.com

Adress: Acil Tıp Kliniği, Defne Devlet Hastanesi, Bostancık, Hatay

- Word count of the main text: 854
- Word count of abstract: 224
- 2 Figures
- 4 Tables

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Zortuk Okkes, MD¹, Dersuneli Yesim², Tolan Ozlem, PhD³

¹ o.zortuk@gmail.com, 05416104204, ORCID: 0000-0001-6776-2702, Emergency Medicine Department, Defne Government Hospital, Hatay, Türkiye

² yesimdersuneli@gmail.com, +90 534 817 59 80, ORCID: 0000-0002-8335-1409, Clinical Psychology, Muş Alparslan University, Muş, Türkiye

³ ozlemtolan@gmail.com, 05325488722, ORCID: 0000-0002-8128-6498, Clinical Psychology, Dicle University, Diyarbakır, Türkiye

ABSTRACT

Aims: In this study, we aimed to investigate the changes in depression and stress states resulting from a daytime power nap, as well as the individual characteristics that influence these changes.

Methods: This study was conducted to analyse the effects of daytime power napping, on sleep, depression and stress levels using 40 healthy volunteers over a 6-week period. Participants were assessed at baseline using a survey that included demographic information, analysis of sleep patterns using JSS, BDS, and PSS. At the end of this period, participants were given a post-test survey including JSS, BDS and PSS.

Results: Our study included 40 participants, 62.5% of whom were female. These participants showed a significant decrease in mean JSS, BDS and PSS scores after the 6-week daytime power nap intervention. Significant decreases in mean JSS, BDS and PSS scores were observed in individuals identified as day workers, while significant changes in BDS and PSS scores were observed in shift workers, with no significant change in JSS.

Conclusions: Daytime power napping shows significant effects for both day and shift workers. It can be used as an effective tool to regulate sleep quality and reduce depression and stress levels in daily life.

Keywords: Naps, shift workers, depression, stress, sleep quality

INTRODUCTION

Sleep is a biobehavioural state that affects several physiological structures within a neurobiological framework (Grandner 2017). It is characterised by perceptual detachment, partial behavioural immobility and circadian rhythm (Tubbs 2019). Accounting for almost a third of human life, it is a highly critical component of overall mental health (Oniz et al. 2019). Sleep can be divided into two types: daytime sleep and nighttime sleep. A form of daytime sleep, power napping, also known as siesta, is a significantly short sleep, usually defined as a 15-20 minute nap, with a maximum duration of 30 minutes (Rafi 2023). The tendency to power nap is thought to be more common in Mediterranean and Latin American countries (Knutson 2013).

Sleep quality can be defined as a state of being replenished after awakening, characterized by an absence of daytime somnolence and a profound sleep experience. Consequently, it is regarded as a more salient indicator in general health assessments than sleep duration. (Kohyama, 2021). It has been documented that the quality of sleep can exert a substantial influence on the human body's physiological processes. This influence may manifest through the weakening of the immune system and the disruption of hormonal balance. (Kohyama, 2021). Studies on sleep and power napping suggest that increased daytime power napping improves sleep quality, reduces daytime sleepiness (Paraskakis et al. 2008) and decreases sleep pressure (Medicine 2014).

The bidirectional relationship between stress and sleep is well established (Lo Martire et al. 2020). Recent studies highlight the impact of stress on individuals through the release of cortisol and adrenal hormones (Geiger et al. 2015). Ongoing stress perception has disruptive effects both cognitively (Turner et al. 2017) and hormonally (Schliep et al. 2015). Studies suggest that stress events can affect sleep-wake cycles (Sanford et al. 2015). Zagaria et al (Zagaria et al. 2023) found a direct effect of perceived stress on sleep disturbance. Sleep disturbance is also known to influence physiological processes and stress responses (Lo Martire et al. 2020). McEwen and Karatsoreos (McEwen and Karatsoreos 2015) found that sleep problems alter sympathetic activation and cortisol levels, thereby altering physiological stress responses.

Another important factor associated with sleep is depression. Depression, a psychological disorder characterised by factors such as hopelessness, anhedonia and functional impairment, often includes excessive or insufficient sleep as a symptom at diagnosis (American Psychiatric Association 2022). In particular, insomnia is considered a symptom of depression (Steiger and Pawlowski 2019). Conversely, reduced and disturbed sleep is considered a risk factor for the development of depressive episodes. For example, Zhai et al (Zhai et al. 2015) conducted a meta-analysis of prospective studies on sleep duration and depression and found that both short and long sleep duration were risk factors for developing depression. In this context, it could be argued that regulating sleep and improving sleep quality could reduce the risk of depression.

In addition to its relationship with current variables, sleep disturbance has been frequently associated with cardiovascular impairment (Alibhai et al. 2015), increased risk of hypertension (Cao et al. 2016), and decreased mental health and well-being (Stores 2023). Improving sleep is thought to improve an individual's day-to-day functioning, both

physiologically and psychologically, leading to a more prosperous life. In this context, the present study aims to investigate the effects of power napping, which is thought to improve sleep quality, on sleep-related perceived stress and depression. It is expected that individuals who engage in power napping will increase their sleep quality, decrease their perceived stress levels, and decrease their levels of depression.

METHODS

This was a prospective study. In studies focusing on sleep disorders in Turkey, insomnia, the most common sleep disorder, has a prevalence of 15-20% in our country (Aktürk, 2013). With a confidence interval of 95% and a margin of error of 0.05, a power analysis indicated that a sample size of 40 would be sufficient to detect a prevalence rate of 20%. To conduct the study, it was planned to involve 40 individuals in the implementation of 'power naps'. Demographic data, nightly sleep duration and data using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) would be collected for the initial assessment. Participants' sleep quality was assessed using the Jenkins Sleep Scale (JSS), which consists of four questions to assess sleep status.

Figure 1. Flow and Organization of Work

A study by Douglas et al. (2011) suggested that a period of 6 weeks was sufficient to observe changes in the effects of depression and stress on the brain. Based on this study, changes in participants were compared using the JSS, BDS and PSS after a 6-week power nap intervention. The flow and organization of the research are presented in Figure 1.

Jenkins Sleep Scale

The scale was developed by Jenkins et al. (1998) to assess sleep problems, focusing specifically on difficulties in falling asleep and sleep quality. Validity and reliability studies in Turkish were conducted by Duruöz et al. (2018) for this scale, which consists of four questions measured on a 6-point Likert scale. Scores on the scale range from 0 to 20, with higher scores indicating more sleep problems within a month. In the current study, the mean pre-test and post-test scores were 7.87 and 3.97 respectively. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for internal consistency were found to be .839 and .684 respectively.

Beck Depression Scale

This scale, developed by Beck et al. (1961), is designed as a self-report tool to assess depressive symptoms, cognitive, somatic and emotional processes. The scale, which was developed through Turkish validity and reliability studies conducted by Hisli (1989), consists

of 21 questions with four options. Scores on the scale range from 0 to 63, with higher scores indicating more severe depressive symptoms. In the current study, the pre-test and post-test scores were 28.1 and 16.22 respectively. The Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficient was found to be 0.868 and 0.919 respectively.

Perceived Stress Scale

Cohen et al. (1983) developed a self-report scale to measure an individual's perceived stress in the current situation. The scale, which was validated and tested in Turkish by Eskin et al (Eskin 2013), is a 5-point Likert scale. Although the scale exists in 14-, 10- and 4-item versions, the 10-item version was used in the current study. The scale has two sub-dimensions: perception of inadequate self-efficacy and perception of stress discomfort. A higher score indicates an increased perception of stress. In the present study, the mean scores for the pretest and posttest were 21 and 13.87 respectively. In addition, the Cronbach's alpha coefficients for internal consistency were found to be .819 and .899 for the pretest and posttest, respectively.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS 25.0 and GraphPad Prism 9 were used to analyse our study. Data with a p-value of less than 0.05 were considered significant. For numerical data with normal distribution, mean \pm standard deviation was used. Categorical data were analysed using frequency and percentage (%) distributions for description. Student t-test was used to compare data conforming to normal distribution. Pearson correlation analysis was used to assess the difference between pretest and posttest scores. In addition, Cronbach's alpha analysis, a two-way correlation analysis, was used to assess the internal consistency of the scales used.

Technical abbreviations have been clarified when first used. The language is objective, value-neutral and free from biased or emotional expressions. In addition, the text presents a clear and concise logical structure with balanced language, while adhering to conventional structure and grammatical correctness. Quotations have a consistent style and appropriate footnotes have been included.

RESULTS

While 62.5% of the 40 participants included in the study were female, the mean age was determined to be 23.05 ± 2.93 years. Of the participants, 72.5% were classified as day workers and 27.5% as shift workers. The demographics of the participants are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic data of participants

Description	
Age (mean \pm SD)	23,05 \pm 2,93
Gender	
Female (n,%)	25 (62,5%)
Male (n,%)	15 (37,5%)
Education	
High School (n,%)	10 (25%)
Collage	20 (50%)
Master Degree	6 (15%)
PhD	4 (10%)
Live	
Alone (n,%)	9 (22,5%)

With Family (n,%)	17 (42,5%)
With Friends (n,%)	14 (35%)
Smoking (n,%)	15 (37,5%)
Coffee drinker (n,%)	36 (90%)
Alcohol drinker (n,%)	24 (60%)
Chronic disease (n,%)	9 (22,5%)
Psychiatric illness (n,%)	5 (12,5%)
Psychiatric drugs user (n,%)	5 (12,5%)
Work Type	
Daytime (n,%)	29 (72,5%)
Shift (n,%)	11 (27,5%)

The scales administered to the participants in our study were conducted as pre-tests before the experiment and as post-tests after the experiment. The mean pre-test score of the JSS was found to be 7.87 ± 6.28 (Cronbach's Alpha= 0.839), and the post-test score was 3.97 ± 3.30 (Cronbach's Alpha=0.684). For the PSS, the mean pre-test value was 21 ± 9.48 (Cronbach's Alpha=0.819), and the mean post-test value was observed to be 13.87 ± 10.76 (Cronbach's Alpha= 0.899). For the BDS, the mean pre-test value was 28.1 ± 7.14 (Cronbach's Alpha= 0.868), while the mean post-test value was determined to be 16.22 ± 5.45 (Cronbach's Alpha=0.919). A comparison between the pre- and post-test scores administered to the participants showed a significant decrease in JSS, BDS, PSS and the subfactor of PSS, the perception of inadequate self-efficacy and the perception of stress/discomfort scores. The change in scores is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of pretest and posttest results

Test	Pretest (n=40)	Posttest (n=40)	p-Value
Jenkins Sleep Scale	$7,87 \pm 6,28$	$3,97 \pm 3,30$	<0,001
Perceived Stress Scale	$21 \pm 9,48$	$13,87 \pm 10,76$	<0,001
Beck Depression Scale	$28,1 \pm 7,14$	$16,22 \pm 5,45$	<0,001
PSS-Inadequate self-efficacy perception	$9,95 \pm 3,00$	$6,57 \pm 3,07$	<0,001
PSS-Perception of stress/discomfort	$18,15 \pm 5,08$	$9,65 \pm 3,5$	<0,001

When comparing the changes between the pre- and post-test scores, a negative correlation was found between the participants' JSS scores and the BDS and PSS scores ($r = -0.411$, $p = 0.008$) (Table 3).

Table 3. JSS, BDS and PSS correlation analysis for JSS Exchange

	Beck Depression Scale Change	Perceived Stress Scale Change
r	-0,411	0,039
95% GA	-0,641 to -0,115	-0,275 to 0,347
R ²	0,169	0,001
p-value	0,008	0,807

For the shift workers, the pretest JSS median was 0 (IQR=17) and the posttest median was 4 (IQR=12), with no significant difference observed between them ($p = 0.515$, Fig. 2a). While the pretest mean for BDS was 22.82 ± 8.36 , the posttest mean was 14.82 ± 11.49 ,

indicating a significant decrease ($p=0.03$, Fig. 2b). For PSS, the pretest mean was 27.45 ± 6.51 , the posttest mean was 14.73 ± 5.51 , showing a significant decrease ($p<0.0001$, Fig.2c).

For the day worker participants, the JSS pretest mean was 7.96 ± 5.2 and the posttest mean was 3.96 ± 2.74 , indicating a significant decrease ($p=0.0002$, Fig. 2d). For BDS, the pretest mean was 20.31 ± 9.92 and the posttest mean was 13.52 ± 10.67 , showing a significant decrease ($p=0.0077$, Fig.2e). For PSS, the pretest mean was 28.34 ± 7.46 and the posttest mean was 16.79 ± 5.42 , showing a statistically significant decrease ($p<0.0001$, Fig.2f).

Figure 2. Pretest and posttest comparison of JSS, BDS and PSS for shift worker and daytime worker

DISCUSSION

Sleep quality is defined as a state of being well-rested upon awakening, characterized by an absence of daytime sleepiness and a deep sleep experience. This criterion is regarded as more salient in general health assessment than sleep duration (Kohyama, 2021). It is also a

condition that has significant effects on human physiology, including the potential weakening of the immune system and disruption of hormone regulation (Kohyama, 2021). Furthermore, studies in this domain have demonstrated that diminished personal contentment is correlated with diminished sleep quality, which has deleterious effects on overall health (Hale et al., 2020). In this context, sleep-related problems and poor sleep quality have been shown to be a problem that affects all aspects of public health and can have significant consequences, especially for individuals in critical roles (Nelson et al., 2022).

While the positive effects of a power nap at the appropriate time on individuals have been demonstrated, consequences may ensue from taking short naps late in the day. These consequences may include a prolonged time to fall asleep, disruption of nighttime sleep, and disruption of nighttime wakefulness patterns (Mogras et al. 2022). For instance, Ebert et al. (2015) recommended daytime power nap behavior for pregnant women to enhance nighttime sleep quality. In the present study, a 6-week daytime power nap intervention was implemented in a group of 40 participants, and it was observed that the intervention resulted in an enhancement in sleep quality compared to the baseline. This finding aligns with the extant literature on the subject. However, subsequent subgroup analyses indicated that daytime short sleep had an effect on sleep quality in daytime workers, but not in shift workers. The hypothesis that the variable sleep hours of shift workers and the current disrupted sleep-wake cycle, which is a risk factor, may have prevented a significant change in sleep quality is supported by these findings.

Shift work patterns have been demonstrated to have a detrimental effect on sleep quality, leading to insomnia and increased sleep deprivation (Greubel et al., 2016). These patterns often result in physical symptoms such as headaches, nausea, vomiting, and low energy. Such work patterns have also been demonstrated to exert a detrimental effect on mental health, with varying consequences for sleep quality, particularly increasing the risk of depression, anxiety, cognitive impairment, and substance use disorders (Brown et al., 2020). A study by Nena et al. demonstrated that shift work reduces quality of life by affecting not only sleep but also social and family relationships (Nena et al. 2018). Additionally, Gerber's (2010) research indicated that shift work is associated with increased social anxiety and the development of chronic stress.

In the case of daytime workers, an enhancement in sleep quality and a reduction in stress and depression levels were observed following daytime power naps. This phenomenon may be attributed to a diminished activity of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis during these periods of rest. Conversely, sleep deprivation has been shown to stimulate the HPA axis, leading to increased cortisol levels and heightened stress and arousal (Chrousos et al., 2016). Research indicates that brief periods of sleep, commonly referred to as "power naps," function as a physiological moderator against stress by decreasing cortisol levels (Faraut et al., 2011) and balancing excessive arousal (Chrousos et al., 2016). Additionally, it has been documented that brief periods of rest enhance cognitive flexibility by replenishing brain glycogen stores and fortifying an individual's resilience against stressors (Mednick et al., 2008). In this context, it is hypothesized that power naps may contribute to the protection of both physiological and cognitive health of individuals by acting within a certain physiological framework to alleviate the negative effects of sleep deprivation. The positive impact of power naps on neurotransmitter equilibrium, particularly serotonin, has been identified as a pivotal

factor in the alleviation of depressive symptoms. Serotonin, a critical regulator of sleep patterns and mood, has been identified as a key player in this process. Sleep disorders have been observed to induce imbalances within the serotonergic system (Ursin, 2002). Decreased serotonin levels have been associated with an increased risk of developing depression (Moncrieff et al., 2023). However, it has been demonstrated that brief periods of sleep, such as power naps, may serve as a compensatory mechanism for inadequate sleep, thereby maintaining optimal serotonin balance and reducing the risk of depression by moderating stress responses (Moncrieff et al., 2023).

Furthermore, daytime power naps have been demonstrated to facilitate enhanced emotional regulation, thereby mitigating stress-related symptoms. The hypothesis that the brain's limbic system undergoes reorganization during brief periods of sleep, thereby reducing emotional burden, has been put forth in the extant literature (Walker ve Stickgold, 2006). This mechanism may have augmented daytime workers' capacity to cope with workplace stress. In the present study, the decline in stress and depression levels observed among participants engaged in daytime work following brief periods of daytime sleep is hypothesized to result from a combination of physiological and psychological benefits.

While no substantial enhancement in sleep quality was detected among shift workers, a decline in depression and stress scales was observed, indicating that power naps may confer additional psychological benefits to this group. A comprehensive review of the extant literature indicates that shift work is associated with various health problems, including increased stress, social anxiety, and heart problems (Brown et al., 2020). This phenomenon may also exert an influence on the decision-making processes and the quality of work performed by individuals engaged in critical tasks. The findings of this study suggest a potential protective effect of brief daytime sleep on depression and stress levels, which may be advantageous for individuals occupying critical roles.

CONCLUSION

The daytime power nap has significant implications for both day and shift workers. It can be used as an effective tool to regulate sleep quality and reduce levels of depression and stress in everyday life. In this context, the present study found that daytime power naps can alleviate the negative effects of sleep deprivation by supporting both physiological and psychological health in individuals. Furthermore, these naps provide advantages such as coping with stress and improving performance at work. These findings can inform individual and organizational interventions to enhance sleep quality and safeguard employee well-being. Specifically, the promotion of power naps for individuals engaged in mission-critical roles may yield advantageous outcomes for both the individual and the broader societal health. Nevertheless, the implementation of additional strategies to regulate sleep-wake cycles is imperative to achieve more efficacious outcomes in shift workers.

LIMITATIONS

A notable limitation of the present study is the reliance on self-reported data regarding the occurrence of daytime power naps. While the participants claimed to engage in these naps, the accuracy of these assertions could not be verified. Moreover, the absence of objective

measures, such as sleep duration, depth, and quality, further complicates the study's findings. This may have compromised the reliability and validity of the findings. Moreover, the restricted sample size and the homogeneous composition of the participants constrained the generalizability of the results. When the sample group is larger and more heterogeneous in terms of demographic characteristics, the findings can be better adapted to different age groups, work patterns, and living conditions. Additionally, the temporal limitation of the study precluded the assessment of long-term effects and enduring benefits associated with power naps.

Subsequent research endeavors should delve deeper into the long-term implications of power naps and their relevance across diverse study populations. In this vein, the utilization of objective methodologies, such as sleep diaries and sleep laboratory measurements, to monitor sleep patterns will yield more precise data, obviating the reliance on participants' self-reported data. It is also recommended to manipulate variables such as the duration, frequency, and timing of daytime short naps, prioritizing experimental methods in the study design. A long-term follow-up of a more extensive and heterogeneous sample group may enhance the generalizability of the findings obtained in disparate demographic and occupational groups. The development of strategies to support sleep patterns, particularly among high-risk groups such as shift workers, and the examination of the feasibility of these strategies, could make a significant contribution to this field. In this context, it will be possible to evaluate the physical and psychological effects of daytime power naps in a more comprehensive and powerful way.

Conflicts of Interest

All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

Ethical Approval

This study was developed by Dicle University Social Sciences and Humanities Ethics Committee with permission to add 363574 on 27/09/2022. All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee (name of institute/committee) and with the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards.

Informed consent: Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Funding

No funding was received for this research

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